

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

MA in Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge

Final Dissertation

**Extending the Crowdsourced
Open Citations Index codebase
for ingesting citations between
entities without DOIs**

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Abstract

This thesis describes an expansion of the existing CRowdsourced Open Citation Index (CROCI) that extended the capabilities of the existing software from being a purely DOI-to-DOI citation index to being able to create citation data from bibliographic resources identified with any type of ID. This is done through a transformation to MetaIDs generated by using OpenCitations Meta, a metadata database that will contain the bibliographic metadata used in the OpenCitations codebase. The resulting MetaID-to-MetaID citation data can then be processed creating information in RDF triples that can be made available on a RDF triplestore. This data is then made available through a REST API that simplifies the access to data. The software was written in Python and employed Semantic Web technologies. The expansion created will be beneficial for the future of OpenCitations for expanding the capabilities of the infrastructure for ingesting citation data. In the meantime, this software will also be responsible in uploading new data to OpenCitations Meta. This thesis includes a review of the existing literature about citation data, metadata and of the context of the OpenCitations infrastructure. Then, the methodology behind how the logical structure behind the software is explored. The next two chapters describe how the software was implemented, first from a high level perspective, then from a technical point of view. Finally, the computational cost of the process is reviewed.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The objective of this thesis is to expand the existing software for CROCI¹, one of the many OpenCitations (OC) indexes².

CROCI (pronounced /kroki/), the CRowdsourced OpenCitations Index, is the OpenCitations index dedicated to citations deposited by individuals voluntarily. In its first version, willing individuals could make available datasets containing citation indexes in a DOI-to-DOI format (Heibi et al., 2019), where DOI³ (Digital Object Identifier) is a unique identifier that references any kind of object. Users that want to make available their citation data to OpenCitations should first upload the citation data in a CSV file (a non-proprietary file format for tabular data) on websites such as Zenodo⁴ or Figshare⁵, open an issue on Github⁶ and upload their citation data. It is important to note that as statements of facts, citations are not subject to copyright and can thus be published with a CC0⁷ waiver, which makes them available to be processed, while their textual arrangements may be protected.

The issue that laid the foundation of the work described in this thesis is that

¹OpenCitations: CROCI <https://opencitations.net/index/croci>, last accessed 15/10/2022

²OpenCitations Index <https://github.com/opencitations/index>, last accessed 15/10/2022

³DOI <https://dx.doi.org/>, last accessed 15/10/2022

⁴Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> last accessed 19/10/2022

⁵Figshare <https://figshare.com/> last accessed 19/10/2022

⁶CROCI on Github <https://github.com/opencitations/croci/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁷Creative Commons 1.0 Universal <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/> last accessed 15/10/2022

the existing system of DOI-to-DOI citation data cannot be fully representative of the entire research environment. There are multiple reasons for that:

- A number of resources lack DOIs or other identifiers because of their publication nature (e.g. WHO and UN reports, government policy documents...) (Peroni & Shotton, 2022b)
- When analysing the distribution of DOIs per research field, it appears that DOIs are much less prevalent for publications in some of them, e.g. in the Humanities, where other identifiers are used for identifying citing and cited works (Gorraiz et al., 2016).
- While the usage of DOIs has been growing globally, publishers in Africa, Asia and Latin America are still somewhat behind. (Boudry & Chartron, 2017)

This thesis work changed the way CROCI processes citation data, from a DOI-to-DOI format (as in Table 1.1) to AnyID-to-AnyID (as in Table 1.2) to address the coverage problem described above. The produced citation data is in a MetaID-to-MetaID format, with the AnyID-to-MetaID mapping performed through communication with OpenCitations Meta, a new collection of bibliographic metadata for the resources involved in the OC infrastructure (Peroni & Shotton, 2020).

This expansion has a critical impact on the possibilities of this citation index. For instance, citations in CROCI can now involve any kind of resource having an identifier such as a DOI, a PubMed ID, a Wikidata entry ID, or a book with an International Standard Book Number (ISBN). The expanded index also allows for mixed citation data (e.g. DOI-to-PMID, ISBN-to-MetaID...) to be generated, something that was not possible in previous indexes. The result is that there are more resources available for creating citation data, given the multiplicity of possible data sources and identifiers. Moreover, OC Meta will allow users to register resources and obtain an identifier to use for data without a persistent identifier.

In addition to the extension of the codebase for handling also non-DOI entities, this work introduces the new version of CROCI's API to access the citation data stored using MetaIDs (a unique identifier generated by OC Meta). This API was created through RAMOSE, the Restful API Manager Over SPARQL Endpoints, a software that is used for the creation of easy-to-use REST APIs to access data

available on SPARQL (Daquino et al., 2022). Part of the thesis work was carried out during an internship at the Digital Humanities Advance Research Centre (/DH.ARC⁸), during which I was tasked with the packaging of the RAMOSE⁹ library, with the creation of a documentation and debugging.

This thesis is organised in five parts. First, the Literature Review section contains state-of-the-art information about the existing citation indexes (from OpenCitations and not), as well as OC Meta and the OCDM. Chapter 3 describes the methodology followed in the expansion of CROCI, including the step-by-step description of the manipulation of data in the process. In Chapter 4, the theoretical approach to expanding CROCI is explained. Chapter 5 contains the technical details for developing CROCI. Finally, in Chapter 6, I evaluated its computational cost when running the process.

citing_id	citing_publication_date	cited_id	cited_publication_date
10.25333/BGFG-D241	2018-12	https://doi:10.25333/C3NK88	2017

Table 1.1. Example of an input table from CROCI before the expansion

citing_id	citing_publication_date	cited_id	cited_publication_date
doi:10.1098/rstb.2017.0432 meta:br/0608	2013	pmid:11620121 wikidata:Q34097010	1979

Table 1.2. Example of an input table from CROCI after the expansion

⁸/DH.ARC <https://centri.unibo.it/dharc/en> last accessed 19/10/2022

⁹RAMOSE <https://github.com/opencitations/ramose> last accessed 15/10/2022

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter is an introduction to the world of scholarly metadata for what it pertains OpenCitations (OC). The first section introduces the importance of citations data. The second gives an overview regarding the gathering process of bibliographic metadata. The third introduces OpenCitations, the OpenCitations Data Model, OC Meta and discusses the services used in the development of this thesis work.

2.1 Citations

A bibliographic citation can be defined as

"[...] a conceptual directional link from a citing entity to a cited entity, for the purpose of acknowledging or ascribing credit for the contribution made by the author(s) of the cited entity. The citing and cited entities may be scholarly publications, on-line documents, blog posts, datasets, or any other authored entities capable of giving or receiving citations." (Peroni & Shotton, 2018)

The role of citations can be various, from supporting a claim, to crediting another author, to tying the citing entity to a cited entity and many more (Harwood, 2009). While not being the only possible indicator of research quality, direct citation data is critical in this sector and has been historically a dominant figure in the evaluation of research output (Shotton, 2013). For example, citation data is at the core of the Impact Factor (IF), one of the most recognised citation metrics in the scholarly community; here, however, lies one of the biggest issues about closed citations (Larivière & Sugimoto, 2019).

The IF is calculated by dividing the number of citations in the Journal Citations Report (JCR) year by the total number of articles published in the two previous years for each journal. This fact introduces multiple problems, one of which is transparency (Larivière & Sugimoto, 2019). Gathering citation data is a huge task, and it has been held close behind paywalls by publishers and aggregators; this does not allow for a transparent evaluation of scientific output and excludes people and organisations that do not have the economic possibility to pay for it. For example, the JCR is compiled using the citations in Web Of Science, the access to which is paid. The same can be said of the rival Scopus, maintained by Elsevier. All of these provide different records, meaning that the resulting metrics can be different and cannot be reliably checked due to the lack of transparency and not being machine-readable data, while being crucial to the careers of researchers (Shotton, 2013, Pranckutė, 2021).

Opening citation data can also foster the discoverability of connected content, especially between disciplines. Creating a climate of cooperation and connection is desirable in the highly specialised research environment of today, and the activities that foster this cooperation should be favoured (Fecher & Friesike, 2014).

To address the problem of closed citation data, there has been a push for publishing citation data as Open Citations. The Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC)¹ was formed with this objective, to promote the creation of citation data following the SSO principles:

- Structure: the data is in machine-readable form. This is advantageous for performing any kind of analysis over it.
- Separable: the data is available without accessing the resource.
- Open: the data are freely accessible and reusable; the most commonly used license is CC0 .

Moreover, in an Open Citation, “the citing and cited entity must be:

- Identifiable – the entities linked by an open citation MUST be clearly identified by using a specific persistent identifier scheme (e.g. a DOI) or a URL;

¹Initiative for Open Citations <https://i4oc.org/> last accessed

- Available – it MUST be possible by resolving their identifiers to obtain the basic metadata of both the entities, sufficient to create or retrieve textual bibliographic references for each of them” (Peroni & Shotton, 2018)

A recently published report states that today, 5 years after the launch of I4OC, more than 60 million papers’ citations are now open (Singh Chawla, 2022). Moreover, since June 2022, Crossref does not allow for references to be closed or limited², meaning that all the references that were deposited in the past and that will be deposited in the future are now open metadata.

2.2 Bibliographic Metadata

Metadata about bibliographic resources has been a subject of interest for libraries and scholars for a while, and the spread of internet has only increased the need for acquiring information about books, articles, and more. At the same time, this has grown the need for standardising information and for creating systems to identify uniquely resources.

Multiple initiatives for standardising metadata production surged especially during the 1990s, from Dublin Core to the evolution of TEI, with a growing discussion on its role (Caplan, 2000, Greenberg, 2003). After the 2000s, the surge of movements and ideals of Open Access, Open Source and Open Science, all of which relied on the internet to thrive, brought new attention to metadata, especially as open metadata, as it could bring even greater benefits to society and to science and visibility to publications (Dugas et al., 2015, Flynn, 2013). The problem of having these many initiatives is the fact that they often are not compatible with each other.

2.2.1 Scholarly Metadata Sources and IDs

Multiple services have been developed for making available bibliographic information on the internet. Since CROCI will need to gather this type of information and

²See <https://i4oc.org/> in the section Participating Publishers

feed it to OC Meta, these services are critical for this work. The ones that have been employed here are the following:

- Crossref³ : a DOI registration agency that has developed as one of the biggest sources of metadata for articles through their public REST API , where information can be obtained free from license. Most of the data on Crossref⁴ is from scholarly articles (Hendricks et al., 2020), but a growing number of different resources is becoming available.
- Wikidata⁵: a free, collaborative secondary database that provides information that supports Wikipedia and the Wikimedia movement in a LOD format. Data can be accessed through their SPARQL endpoint⁶. Wikidata was started in 2012 and data from it has been used for various cases, from studying community practices by editors to Natural Language Processing and bibliometric studies (Mora-Cantalops et al., 2019). Since data from Wikidata is not always precise or well-formed, the use of this source will come under strict control.
- DataCite⁷: another DOI registration agency that makes available its data through a REST API⁸; an important difference from Crossref is that within DataCite a significant number of metadata is from datasets; as an example, DataCite is the agency responsible for registering DOIs in Zenodo (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2017).
- ORCID⁹: an organisation that provides unique identifiers for researchers (ORCID stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID) and connects a record of their publications. By using its API service this information could be

³Crossref <https://www.crossref.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁴Crossref REST API <https://api.crossref.org/> last accessed ...

⁵Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/> last accessed ...

⁶Wikidata Query Service <https://query.wikidata.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁷DataCite <https://datacite.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁸DataCite API <https://api.datacite.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁹ORCID <https://orcid.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

gathered, in particular using the `oc_graphenricher`¹⁰ library, which is used in this work. In ORCID, the link between the author and its publication is usually done by the author themselves, meaning that in some cases authors might not be found by it.

- VIAF¹¹: the Virtual International Authority File, combines multiple name authorities in one Online Computer Library Center hosted website, providing an API. The API is used to look for researchers' ids and is also queried by using the aforementioned `oc_graphenricher` software library. Contrary to ORCID, the VIAF record is generated by an external authority file.

These services and agencies are also responsible for registering identifiers or authority files. Having an identifier is critical for disambiguating individuals or resources that might be homonyms or have multiple names. The IDs employed in CROCI for bibliographic resources are the following:

- DOI, Digital Object Identifier. DOIs are registered by agencies such as CrossRef and DataCite. The DOI system “provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type”¹²; a DOI can be resolved to check for the validity and existence of the referenced resource. A DOI is composed of 10 followed by a period, a prefix and suffix separated by a forward slash (`10.prefix/suffix`)
- QID or Wikidata ID. Prefix: “wikidata”. Since Wikidata IDs might relate to resources that are completely unrelated, a Wikidata ID cannot be alone in the input file. QIDs are provided by wikidata and are composed by a Q followed by an incremental number (`Q12345`). They can be resolved as entities on Wikidata.
- ISBN: International Standard Book Number. It can have two forms, as ISBN10 (for books published until 2007) or ISBN13, depending on the number of cyphers. Each ISBN identifies in a unique way an edition of a book,

¹⁰`oc_graphenricher` https://github.com/opencitations/oc_graphenricher last accessed 17/10/2022

¹¹VIAF <https://viaf.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

¹²DOI <https://dx.doi.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

meaning that if a book has multiple editions, it will have multiple ISBNs associated with it.

- PMID: PubMed Reference Numbers, an identifier asserted by the National Institute of Health National Library of Medicine to publications indexed in PubMed¹³. PMIDs are composed of a sequence of numbers.
- MetaID: MetaIDs. Identifiers generated by OC Meta. A MetaID is composed of an indication of the type of resource followed by a forward slash and 06 followed by a sequence of numbers, not ending with a 0.

While it is possible that resources have multiple identifiers, it is not as common as it should be. This creates systems that often do not talk to each other. An example of this is the data released by Crossref; the citation data that is found there only employs DOIs, just as the citation data from Wikidata is QID-to-QID. This incompleteness is one of the starting points of this work and, in general, of the need for an over-the-parts organisation for managing such data.

2.3 OpenCitations

Opening citation data is the main objective of OpenCitations (OC), a not-for-profit organisation that formally started in 2010, when the first OpenCitation Corpus (OCC) was released (Peroni & Shotton, 2020, Di Giambattista et al., 2022). In the following years, especially after the I4OC, the scope of citation data managed by OC grew significantly. This event sensibilised publishers and the scholarly community to make their citation data openly available through Crossref (Hendricks et al., 2020). Thus, Crossref has become a critical source of citation data, which has been ingested in OC's COCI, now containing more than 1.3 billion citations.

The mission of OC is “to harvest and openly publish accurate and comprehensive metadata describing the world’s academic publications and the scholarly citations that link them, and to preserve ongoing access to this information by secure archiving.” (Peroni, Silvio & Shotton, David, 2022a). The chosen way for the

¹³PMID vs PMCID <https://nexus.od.nih.gov/all/2015/08/31/pmid-vs-pmcid-whats-the-difference/> last accessed 15/10/2022

publication of this data is the Linked Open Data (LOD) format, meaning that the results are released in RDF language with open licenses. The choice of LOD follows a clear idea of creating a rich dataset available to the public that uses widely accepted internet protocols. LOD should follow a 5 star deployment schema¹⁴. These are 5 requirements that maximise the openness of data: publishing data with an open license; available on structured data; available in a non-proprietary open format; use RDF standards, e.g. by denoting things by using URIs; link the data to other data to provide context. The data published in OC follows these criteria.

OCC consists in a collection of Open Citation Data harvested from Open Access literature from PubMed Central and made available in RDF and was later expanded through the cooperation of the University of Oxford and the University of Bologna. The OCC is encoded as Linked Open Data by the means of the OpenCitations Ontology (OCO) (Peroni et al., 2017). This ontology groups information that is contained in the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM) that will be discussed later.

2.3.1 OpenCitation Indexes

This thesis focuses on the expansion of one of the many citation indexes within OC. Each index focuses on the ingestion of data from a different source, and the resulting data is made available in CC0 format.

A feature of OC Indexes is that a citation is not just a property that connects two entities, but a first-class entity that can have properties of its own (Heibi et al., 2019). This allows for citations to exist independently from the published entity and other advantages (Peroni & Shotton, 2018). To uniquely identify the citations, an OCI, the Open Citation Identifier, is produced by encoding the identifiers of the entities involved (Peroni & Shotton, 2019). An OCI contains a prefix that depends on the suppliers involved in creating the citation¹⁵ and a series of numbers generated by using a lookup table¹⁶. OCIs do not allow citations between different types of IDs.

¹⁴<https://5stardata.info/en/> last accessed 15/10/2022

¹⁵The updated list of suppliers can be found here: [Opencitations: OCI http://opencitations.net/oci](http://opencitations.net/oci) last accessed 15/10/2022

¹⁶Lookup table: <https://github.com/opencitations/oci/blob/master/lookup.csv> last accessed 15/10/2022

oci:	prefix for all OCIs
050	prefix for CROCI supplier
153	sequence converted through lookup of citing entity
-	separator
050	prefix for CROCI supplier
2423	sequence converted through lookup of cited entity

Table 2.1. This table shows the elements of an OCI. As an example, the OCI `oci:050221429103811273600060001000802-05022142910381127360006000100080` is the represents the citation between entities `meta/br/0601082` and `meta/br/0601083`

The first citation index produced in OC was COCI (OpenCitations Index of Crossref) (Heibi et al., 2019). COCI processes data made available by Crossref and extracts the DOI-to-DOI citations in it.

The workflow for the creation of COCI is similar to the one of most other indexes in OC, it follows these steps:

1. Data Gathering: Articles in Crossref having a DOI and a reference list are gathered, along with additional information if present (e.g. the publication type, information about the authors, identifiers such as ISSNs and ORCID...).
2. Data Production: In this step , the information retrieved is processed, with an output in three different formats: CSV, RDF, and Scholix¹⁷. The information about the provenance of data is also created; this accounts for the information about its creation and is critical for assessing the entities involved in the creation, modification and movement of data (Simmhan et al., 2005, Gupta, 2009).
3. Updating the triplestore: The RDF file is used to update the OC Triplestore (Heibi et al., 2019)

Data in COCI can be gathered or queried via a SPARQL endpoint¹⁸ and using

¹⁷Scholix is a framework for sharing information "about links between scholarly literature and research data". <http://www.scholix.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

¹⁸OpenCitations Indexes SPARQL Endpoint <https://opencitations.net/index/sparql> last accessed 15/10/2022

the dedicated REST API service¹⁹ created using RAMOSE.

The second index produced by OC is CROCI. The trigger of this work, as Heibi et al. (2019) showed, was a problem in the data of COCI: relying on publishers to open their citations in order to be included in COCI resulted in citation data absence of important publishers. CROCI was presented as an alternative and a possible solution to overcome this limit. Considering the fact that citation data are a statement of fact, therefore not subject to copyright, it is possible for researchers to publish their scholarly citation data even if the article is published in a closed journal (that does not publish the list of references). To make the data available, it needs to be in CSV or Scholix format, hosted on a service such as Zenodo²⁰ or Figshare²¹. Anyone interested in making such data available is also asked to provide an ORCID ID. Since CROCI is the main subject of this thesis, this topic will be expanded and discussed further in the upcoming sections.

As (Peroni & Shotton 2022b) states, the objective of OC for the future years includes the expansion of coverage both in the sense of fields (e.g. the humanities) as well as the broadening of coverage for citation data not using DOIs. To do so, multiple new indexes are being created. Among these are NOCI, the National Institute of Health Open Citation Collection, part of a previous thesis work by Moretti (2022), that manages PMID-to-PMID citations, DOCI, the Datacite Open Citation Index, and others (Peroni & Shotton, 2022b).

2.3.2 Other Citation Indexes

OC indexes are not the only citation indexes that exist today; there are multiple initiatives, some of which also using Semantic Web technologies. Some examples include:

¹⁹REST API for COCI, the OpenCitations index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI references <https://opencitations.net/index/coci/api/v1>

²⁰Zenodo is a free to use service for hosting data up to 50 GB that also provides a unique DOI registered on DataCite. Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

²¹Figshare <https://figshare.com/> last accessed 15/10/2022

- Wikicite²²: a Wikimedia initiative that exploits the Wikidata LOD infrastructure, it started to add sources to facts in Wikipedia²³, and is now used “to develop open citations and linked bibliographic data to serve free knowledge”.
- Biotea²⁴: an initiative that processed the fulltext open access information from PubMed Central to create an RDF dataset to allow free extraction of information (Garcia et al., 2018).
- ScholeXplorer²⁵: a result of the RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) Working Group²⁶, it connects databases from between not just articles but literature objects from multiple sources, OpenAire, Crossref and Datacite.
- The Linked Open Citation Database(Lauscher et al., 2018), a project for the creation of a LOD database following the OpenCitations Data Model from the resources of libraries.
- Agricola²⁷: a database containing citations and bibliographic records from the from the National Agricultural Library in the US.

2.3.3 The OpenCitations Data Model and the SPAR Ontologies

The OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM)²⁸, described by Daquino et al (2020a, 2020b), is used to model all the bibliographic and citation entities created within OC as RDF triples. It uses the SPAR (Semantic Publishing and Referencing)

²²Wikicite <https://meta.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=WikiCite&oldid=23440846> last accessed 15/10/2022

²³Wikicite (2006 proposal) [https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Wikicite_\(2006_proposal\)](https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Wikicite_(2006_proposal)) last accessed 15/10/2022

²⁴Biotea <https://biotea.github.io/>

²⁵ScholeXplorer <https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu/>

²⁶Scholix Working Group, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-scholarly-link-exchange-scholix-wg> last accessed 15/10/2022

²⁷Agricola <https://agricola.nal.usda.gov/>, last accessed 15/10/2022

²⁸Data Model <https://opencitations.net/model> last accessed 15/10/2022

Ontologies²⁹. These ontologies, as the name suggests, are used in the context of ‘semantic publishing’, which can be defined as:

“[...] anything that enhances the meaning of a published journal article, facilitates its automated discovery, enables its linking to semantically related articles, provides access to data within the article in actionable form, or facilitates integration of data between papers” (Shotton, 2009)

SPAR ontologies contain multiple modules that accurately represent bibliographic resources and their components (Peroni & Shotton, 2018).

The main interplay between SPAR ontologies in the OCDM can be seen in Figure 2.1. The SPAR Ontologies used in OCDM are:

Figure 2.1. Graffoo representation of the OCDM (Source: Daquino et al., 2022a)

²⁹SPAR Ontologies <http://www.sparontologies.net/> last accessed 15/10/2022

- CiTO³⁰ (Citation Typing Ontology): this is an ontology “that enables characterization of the nature or type of citations, both factually and rhetorically”. Citations in CiTO are described as a first-class data entity, a `cito:Citation`. This class also has some subclasses for special types of citations, e.g. `cito:SelfCitation` for cases in which the citing entities have something significant in common, such as being in the same journal. A citation has the attributes `cito:hasCitingEntity` and `cito:hasCitedEntity` that describe the two entities involved in the citation as well as a possible characterisation (Peroni & Shotton, 2012).
- FaBiO³¹ (FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology), an ontology for describing entities that are publishable "and that contain or are referred to by bibliographic references.". FaBiO follows the FRBR schema of Works, Expressions, Manifestations and Items. This permits to hold information about both bibliographic resources and their embodiment (Peroni & Shotton, 2012).
- BiRO³² (Bibliographic Reference Ontology) is employed “to define bibliographic records, bibliographic references, and their compilation into bibliographic collections and bibliographic lists, respectively.” This ontology, combined with C4O, describes the context of references and bibliographic records (Di Iorio et al., 2014).
- DEO³³ (Discourse Elements Ontology) provides a structured vocabulary to describe rhetorical subdivisions in a document.
- PRO³⁴ (Publishing Roles Ontology), an ontology “that provides characterisation of the roles of agents involved in publishing an article”. (Peroni et al., 2012). An important aspect in PRO is that the role held by an agent is contextualised in a time interval.

³⁰CiTO, the Citation Typing Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/cito> last accessed 15/10/2022

³¹FaBiO, the FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/fabio> last accessed 15/10/2022

³²BiRO, the Bibliographic Reference Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/ biro> last accessed 15/10/2022

³³DEO, the Discourse Elements Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/deo> last accessed 15/10/2022

³⁴PRO, the Publishing Roles Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/pro> last accessed 15/10/2022

- C4O³⁵ (Citation Counting and Context Characterization Ontology), an ontology that provides pointers and counters for citation data (Di Iorio et al., 2014).
- DataCite Ontology³⁶, an ontology that delivers the DataCite Metadata Schema in RDF. This is especially useful in this context as it provides a system for providing information about the schema and identifiers used for identifying a resource through `datacite:usesSchemaIdentifier`.

Within each RDF Dataset, the information about the provenance of data is stored using PROV-O³⁷, an ontology that models the provenance information as an interplay between a `prov:Agent` to which is attributed a `prov:Entity` and who is associated with a `prov:Activity` within a certain timeframe (Figure 2.2). This aspect is important due to the changing nature of data and the responsibilities for said data.

2.3.4 OpenCitations Meta

An important project from OC is the creation of OpenCitations Meta, a metadata database for resources involved in the OC infrastructure, first described in (Peroni & Shotton, 2020) and developed in (Mariani, 2020), now in production and expected to be available by the end of the year 2022. Along with the processing of already existing information openly available from Crossref, one of the objectives of OC Meta is to allow the intervention of users in uploading the data to complete missing information about bibliographic sources. The metadata to be uploaded on OC Meta should follow the indications in (Massari & Heibi, 2022).

The software developed for OC Meta³⁸ performs the data curation and knowledge extraction from a CSV file containing metadata information about a resource and creates RDF files that are uploaded to a Blazegraph³⁹ triplestore. OC Meta

³⁵C4O, Citation Counting and Context Characterization Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/c4o> last accessed 15/10/2022

³⁶The DataCite Ontology <http://purl.org/spar/datacite> last accessed 15/10/2022

³⁷The PROV-O Ontology <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/> last accessed 15/10/2022

³⁸OpenCitations Meta Software https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta last accessed 15/10/2022

³⁹Blazegraph <https://blazegraph.com/> last accessed 15/10/2022

Figure 2.2. The relationship between Entity, Agent and Activity in PROV-O. Source: Lebo et al., 2013

can gather information regarding the different entities involved in the publication of resources, such as the authors and venues, each of which is assigned a unique ID.

Each entity in OC Meta is identified by an URI, Uniform Resource Identifier, which allows for linking resources and information in the RDF triplestore. These identifiers, created by OC Meta, are called MetaIDs, that here are used for the creation of CROCI's input tables to map the given entities to their corresponding a MetaIDs. The Curator module within OC Meta is the main responsible actor of the records and ID deduplication, that uses a strict approach on IDs for entity deduplication (Mariani, 2020). The decision-taking about the creation of a new MetaID for an entity is described in Figure 2.3. An example of a possible issue emerged when gathering information from Wikidata: the possibility of having overlapping IDs, e.g. ISBNs, for the container and the articles, creating a redundancy in the data. Such problems need a human intervention to be handled.

MetaIDs uniquely identify the resources that are involved in the publication of the resource, and thus can refer to multiple elements (es. <https://w3id.org/oc/meta/id/061103>). For simplicity, from here on MetaIDs are represented either with the prefix "meta:". Depending on their nature, they have a different prefix:

- **br** for bibliographic resources, identifying both the resources given in input and characters involved in their publication like the venue and the volume.
- **ra** for responsible agent, identifying agents with their name and ID. This agent might be either an individual or an organisation.
- **ar** for agent role, clarifying the role of a responsible agent in a certain time constraint.
- **re** for resource embodiment, identifying the material manifestation of a bibliographic resource.
- **id** for identifiers, that associates each resource to an external identifier. (Mariani, 2020, p.35)

OC Meta manages the IDs for resources by using the DataCite ontology. The connection between a resource and its ID is managed by means of the `meta:id` identifier, which is connected to the schema used by using the `datacite:usesIdentifierSchema` property to the type of ID employed by it (e.g. `datacite:isbn`) and the `literal:hasLiteralValue` to the string containing the actual value for it (figure 2.4).

br	prefix for a Bibliographic Resource
060	prefix for MetaIDs
1053	an incremental number for each entity assigned.

Table 2.2. This table shows the elements of a MetaID. This entity, `br/060105`, represents an expression of a bibliographic resource.

Prefixes	
fabio:	http://purl.org/spar/fabio/
meta:	https://w3id.org/oc/meta/
rdfs:	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
datacite:	http://purl.org/spar/datacite/
literal:	http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/

Figure 2.4. The reification of IDs in OC Meta

The deployment of OC Meta will allow OC to have three major advantages:

- The database will store in-house and processed in a desired format all the metadata for resources involved in citations, including information about authors. Self-hosting such metadata presents an advantage in performance for OC's APIs; since now they use external services to gather bibliographic information, moving this service internally to the server will improve the performance of such operations.
- OC will be able to process citations involving publications lacking DOIs, such in the case of the expansion of CROCI described in this work.
- It will allow OC to store metadata for publications without incoming citations at present. This is important because a significant amount of publications do not have, at the moment, information about incoming citations, but they might receive it in the future thanks to new indexes. An example might be an article with a registered DOI that receives citations from an article with a PMID; within COCI, this paper might receive no citations, but this does not mean it has no citations overall (Peroni & Shotton, 2022b).

In the case of CROCI, the current software interfaces with OC Meta especially for the necessity of ID mapping. This aspect is crucial for CROCI because any resource can be assigned a MetaID, meaning that by integrating OC Meta in the workflow any resource identified by an ID can be mapped to a MetaID. By transforming the input table into same ID citation data, they can be integrated in the OC Index workflow and have an OCI assigned to them. The interface also creates a double benefit: CROCI gathers MetaIDs that are used for the creation of citation data and OC Meta ingests information from multiple sources. Moreover, the mapping addresses the problem of overlapping citation data in the OC indexes, and was already in place in (Moretti, 2022).

2.3.5 Querying data from OpenCitations

The data released by OC, always in CC0 format, can be queried in multiple ways. These services are free and open to use:

- The OC SPARQL endpoints, where RDF data from the OCC, from the indexes and from the Corpus Citations in Context data can be queried.
- The OC REST APIs, created with RAMOSE for each index in OC. To query these services, users are encouraged to create their own Access Token. These APIs also employ other services to gather metadata about publications.
- The OC Search Interfaces, user-friendly instruments that allow users to search data in the OC datasets and to visualise it.

Data from OC was also available through public data dumps available on the website⁴⁰.

These APIs often exploited data made available from other services; however, with the creation of OC Meta, these services will all be contained within the OC field, guaranteeing the quality and consistency of the data between them. Part of this thesis work will be the expansion of the existing CROCI API.

⁴⁰OpenCitations - Downloads <https://opencitations.net/download> last accessed 15/10/2022

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter presents the methodology for the expansion of CROCI from DOI-to-DOI citations to AnyID-to-AnyID. This change in the functionality required multiple scripts to be created and nested within the OC framework. What this means is that a number of good practices for software development should be followed, such as favouring code reusability, as in “don’t reinvent the wheel” and “don’t be a perfectionist” principles (Prlić & Procter, 2012), as well as following the conventions and standards employed through the software built until now.

Before, when citation data was only DOI-based, the process was like the one indicated above for COCI, with the difference that data in CROCI is crowdsourced via GitHub Issues. This method for gathering the data does not change, although the integration of citation data for non-DOIs required a change in the general workflow.

Expanding the software for managing multiple citation IDs improved significantly the potential of the citation software within OC, to the point of possibly including any published source that has an ID. This prerequisite is the only way to avoid repetition, and, when it will be possible to register crowdsourced data on OC Meta, it will be possible to obtain an ID for any resource.

It is important to note that the gathered citation data here does not come from a single source, such as other indexes, but is crowdsourced from scholars who decide to make the data available. This creates the possibility of having heterogeneous data inputs, which should be considered when using this software. As an example, CSV files might use different encodings or separators, meaning that a preparatory

data cleaning step preliminary to this workflow should be expected.

As anticipated, citation data in OC is stored with OCIs. These only manage citation data with the same ID for citing and cited. This required the creation of an ID that would, in turn, act as a bridge between any citation data. The solution provided in this thesis involved OC Meta as well the produced data are given to OC Meta to be further integrated in OC as new data that could have been otherwise not present.

This is done through a preprocessing action. The way this process can be envisioned is as a data extraction, enrichment, and recreation pipeline that starts with an AnyID-to-AnyID citation table, validates the IDs used (meaning that there is correspondence between an ID and its expected value, e.g. a QID must start with an uppercase “q” followed by a sequence of numbers), gathers information from APIs and endpoints (e.g. bibliographic information from Crossref and DataCite), creates a table to be uploaded to OC Meta, and takes the output of the processing of OC Meta (a CSV table), gathers the MetaIDs and generates a new MetaID-to-MetaID citation table. The new citations created are to be made available through a REST API.

The workflow for the creation and data publication of CROCI is represented in seven steps. First, the input table row is parsed. The IDs in input are validated and new IDs are gathered. Then, the information about the resources are gathered from existing services (Wikidata, Crossref and Datacite for now). The third step is launching OC Meta. In this process, we gather the MetaIDs, which are then used for creating a new table. The new input table is then parsed for the creation of citation data, and the resulting file is made available through the API.

To make the workflow understandable in from start to finish, this section will follow the evolution of a sample input table (Table 3.1).

citing_id	citing_publication_date	cited_id	cited_publication_date
doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60424-9	2008	pmid:16635265	2006
wikidata:Q46061806; pmid:18374409		doi:10.1007/BF02754849	1985
isbn:978-1-4724-2375-7	2017	isbn:0-300-07687-8	1999

Table 3.1. Example of input table for the current version of CROCI

3.1 Validating and Gathering IDs

First, we need to process row by row the ids of the citations. The IDs are contained in the `citing_id` and `cited_id` columns and should have a prefix followed by colon (e.g. “doi:”) and separated from each other with a semicolon, as shown before in table 3.1.

The IDs supported by the current instance of CROCI are shown in table 3.2 with the relative prefixes used and some notes for the usage. In particular, QIDs are not considered as assertive as the other IDs because of the sometimes problematic quality of data in Wikidata (Shenoy et al., 2022, Färber et al., 2017).

ID	Prefix	Notes
DOI: Digital Object Identifier	doi	
QID: Wikidata ID	wikidata	Since Wikidata IDs can refer to basically anything (see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2640 , which refers both to an asteroid and to a scholarly article), they cannot be alone.
ISBN: International Standard Book Number	isbn	Can be in either in ISBN10 or ISBN13 form. If an ISBN is present, it should still have the hyphens; they will later be removed
PMID: PubMed Ids	pmid	
MetaID: MetaID	meta	
ORCID: Open Researcher and Contributor ID	orcid	
VIAF: Virtual International Authority File	viaf	

Table 3.2. Information about IDs employed in CROCI with notes on their use.

The first step is to validate them. This process is done by using `IdentifierManager` instances. These scripts are pieces of software that normalises the existing IDs. With this measure, the insertion of badly formed IDs in the system is prevented.

Figure 3.1. Example of the outputs of a `normalise` method of `IdentifierManager` classes. It is possible to specify whether to keep or not the prefix of the identifier.

If any series of ID in the `citing_id` or `cited_id` columns for the row cannot be normalised, the citation is not processed and the script moves to the next row. If both IDs are correctly processed, then we move to the next substep: gathering new IDs.

Since a single resource might have multiple IDs but might not be specified in a field, we retrieve from Wikidata the other possible IDs that might be there. This is done through a SPARQL query to the endpoint¹; if no result is found and any character is a lowercase letter, the query is repeated with all uppercase. This is done because Wikidata sometimes stores DOIs in uppercase. The IDs are then kept in a dictionary to speed up the process if the same ID is found again, avoiding the repetition by means of an integer pointer to the position of the found ID (e.g., the first ID parsed has the index 0, the second 1. . .). In the table we were following above, we found that the article associated with the DOI 10.1016/s0140-6736(08)60424-9 and the PMID 18374409 are the same, so the id is not repeated.

¹Wikidata SPARQL Endpoint, <https://query.wikidata.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

IDs	Index
'doi': '10.1016/s0140-6736(08)60424-9', 'wikidata': 'Q46061806', 'pmid': '18374409'	0
'pmid': '16635265', 'wikidata': 'Q34768028', 'doi': '10.1186/1475-2875-5-33'	1
'doi': '10.1007/bf02754849', 'wikidata': 'Q41385255', 'pmid': '3910572'	2
'isbn': '978-1-315-61467-0 978-1-4724-2375- 7', 'wikidata': 'Q55829735'	3
'isbn': '0-300-07687-8', 'wikidata': 'Q42348788'	4

Table 3.3. Identifiers and indexes from Table 3.1 normalised and complete.

3.2 Gathering Bibliographic information

After the IDs are found, the process moves to finding more bibliographic information depending on the available IDs:

- If there is a DOI, Crossref’s REST API is queried first. Then, if no information is gathered, we move to DataCite’s REST API.
- If there is a QID, Wikidata’s SPARQL endpoint is queried.
- If neither a QID nor a DOI are present, no information can be gathered.

When a result is obtained from an API or endpoint, we need to extract the information from it in a way that is consistent with OC’s metadata standards, e.g. by mapping the resource types to the ones used in OC. In general, precision is favoured over recall for this process, as it is possible to have a lot of noise in the information retrieved. Therefore, especially for Wikidata, the resources are queried using strictly semantically correct properties, avoiding properties that might be generic. As an example, there are two possible ways to indicate an author, depending on the presence of a Wikidata entry for them; by using the P50² property to the author, to which the name and surname may be indicated, or P2093³, which

²author - Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P50> last accessed

³author name string - Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P2093>, last accessed 15/10/2022

uses only the string. In the current version, the names are retrieved only for the first case, to avoid the risk of collecting bad data.

If no information about the dates of the articles is found, the ones given in the input file are considered correct.

After the bibliographic information is gathered, we enrich the information about the authors. This is done through ORCID and the VIAF’s APIs. The identifiers are added in square brackets after the names of the authors in the form `family name, given name [orcid:id viaf:id]` E.g. `Peroni, Silvio [orcid:0000-0003-0530-4305 viaf:309649450]`. Gathering these IDs strictly depends on the bibliographic resource they are found with, as the ORCID interface uses the identifiers that are present (DOIs and PMIDs), while VIAF uses the title of the resource.

The resulting table will be in the format shown in table 3.4 .

id	title	author	pub_date	venue	volume	issue	page	type	publisher	editor
doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60424-9 wikidata:Q46061806 pmid:18374409	A new global malaria eradication strategy	'Feachem, Richard []; Sabot, Oliver [']*	2008-5	The Lancet [issn:0140-6736]	371	9624	1633-1635	journal article	Elsevier BV [crossref:78]	
pmid:16635265 wikidata:Q34768028 doi:10.1186/1475-2875-5-33	A steep decline of malaria morbidity and mortality trends in Eritrea between 2000 and 2004: the effect of combination of control methods	'Nyarango, Peter M [viaf:56502981]; Gebremeskel, Tewolde [; [...]]*	2006-4-24	Malaria Journal [issn:1475-2875]	5	1		journal article	Springer Science and Business Media LLC [crossref:297]	
doi:10.1007/bf02754849 wikidata:Q41385255 pmid:3910572	'Malaria in India: Past, present and future'	'Choudhury, D. S. [']*	1985-5	The Indian Journal of Pediatrics [issn:0019-5456 issn:0973-7693]	52	3	243-248	journal article	Springer Science and Business Media LLC [crossref:297]	
isbn:978-1-4724-2375-7 wikidata:Q55829735	'The Church at War: The military activities of bishops, abbots and other clergy in England c.900-1200'		2017					book		
isbn:0-300-07687-8 wikidata:Q42348788	The great household in late medieval England	'Woolgar, Chris [viaf:91857312]]*	1999					book		

Table 3.4. Table containing the bibliographic information gathered from APIs and other services

3.3 Launching OC Meta

At this point, the table for OC Meta is ready. Here we need to launch the `MetaProcess` from the `oc_meta` library⁴. Before this passage, a YAML configuration file containing the information for launching the process needs to be created, such as the directories for input and output and the number of cores used. For the testing here, a local Blazegraph database was created with a sample of the OC Meta database.

This passage is critical because it provides the mapping of the input IDs to existing or new MetaIDs, which is then used for the creation of the input citation table.

Once the process is finished, the resulting CSV table (see Table 3.5) contains more information (e.g. pre-existing information from OC Meta, mapping of ISSN and ISBNs, indexing on Crossref...) as well as the MetaIDs for the entities involved.

⁴OC Meta on Github https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta last accessed 15/10/2022

id	title	author	pub_date	venue	volume	issue	page	type	publisher	editor
doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60424-9 wikidata:Q16061806 pmid:18371409	A new global malaria eradication strategy	*Fachem, Richard Sabot, Oliver	2008-5	The Lancet [issn:0140-6736]	371	9624	1633-1635	journal article	Elsevier, BV [crossref:78]	
pmid:16635265 wikidata:Q31768028 doi:10.1186/1475-2875-5-33	A steep decline of malaria morbidity and mortality trends in Eritrea between 2000 and 2004: the effect of combination of control methods	*Nyarango, Peter [uid:5652981]; Gebremeskel, Tewolde	2006-4-24	Malaria Journal [issn:1475-2875]	5	1		journal article	Springer Science and Business Media, LLC [crossref:297]	
doi:10.1007/s00275-010-0140-1 wikidata:Q41385255 pmid:3910572	Malaria in India: Past, present and future*	*Choudhury, D. S.	1985-5	The Indian Journal of Pediatrics [issn:0019-5436 issn:0973-7693]	52	3	243-248	journal article	Springer Science and Business Media, LLC [crossref:297]	
isbn:978-1-4724-2375-7 wikidata:Q55829735	*The Church at War: The military activities of bishops, abbots and other clergy in England c.900-1200*		2017					book		
isbn:0-300-07687-8 wikidata:Q12348788	The great house-hold in late medieval England	*Woodgar, Chris [uid:591857312]*	1990					book		

Table 3.5. Table resulting from the processing of OC Meta

3.4 Creating the new table

The information retrieved is used to create a MetaID-to-MetaID table that the parser processes to create the new citation (Table 3.6). This substitution is not done on the file itself, to avoid confusion and possible irreparable errors, but in a temporary directory.

citing_id	citing_publication_date	cited_id	cited_publication_date
meta:br/0601105	2008-05	meta:br/0601106	2006-04-24
meta:br/0601105	2008-05	meta:br/0601107	1985-05
meta:br/0601108	2017	meta:br/0601109	1999

Table 3.6. The citation table generated by the MetaFeeder after the preprocessing action.

3.5 Parsing the new table

The new table can now be parsed and new citation data is created (Table 3.7). This process is then integrated for creating new citations within the `index` library. The resulting data is validated row per row. The new citation table is prepared to be aligned to the `cito:Citation` type that will happen in the following step.

citing	cited	creation	timespan	journal_sc	author_sc
meta:br/0601067	meta:br/0601068	2008-05	P2Y1M	no	no
meta:br/0601067	meta:br/0601069	2008-05	P23Y0M	no	no
meta:br/0601070	meta:br/0601071	2017	P18Y	no	no

Table 3.7. The result of the processing by the `CROCIParser`

3.6 Creating the citation data and OCIs

The parsed table is used to create a citation table compatible to the OCDM. In particular, the citation information created in CSV (see Table 3.8) and RDF is compliant to the definition of a `cito:citation` and contains the following information:

1. `oci`: the OCI of the citation.

2. citing: the ID of the citing entity.
3. cited: the ID of the cited entity.
4. creation: the date of creation (following the ISO format YYYY-MM-DD) of the citing entity.
5. timespan: the time elapsed between the publication of the citing entities.
6. author self citation: whether the author of the citing entity is the same of the cited entity.
7. journal self citation: whether the citing and cited resource were published in the same journal.

oci	citing	cited	creation	timespan	journal	scauthor	st
05022142910381127360060001000607-05022142910381127360060001000608	meta:br/0601067	meta:br/0601068	2008-05	P2Y1M	no	no	
05022142910381127360060001000607-05022142910381127360060001000609	meta:br/0601067	meta:br/0601069	2008-05	P23Y0M	no	no	
05022142910381127360060001000700-05022142910381127360060001000701	meta:br/0601070	meta:br/0601071	2017	P18Y	no	no	

Table 3.8. Citation data generated with at the conclusion of the citation creation process

3.7 Making available the information

The information gathered will be available through a REST API created through RAMOSE. Through it, a user will be able to retrieve information about:

1. The references of a resource given an ID.
2. The citations to an entity given an ID.
3. The citation given an OCI.
4. The metadata of an entity given an ID.
5. The count of incoming citations to an entity given a ID.
6. The count of outgoing citations of an entity given a ID.

The reason for offering a REST API rather than just a SPARQL endpoint is of convenience for the user. SPARQL technologies are powerful and flexible, but not as used as the APIs and have intricacies that might make users move away. By creating a smaller number of operations with preset SPARQL queries and with powerful possibilities given by parameters, the use of RAMOSE is beneficial for the outreach of this initiative.

Script 3.1. Example of JSON output of the
 api/v1/oci/050221429103811273600060001000607-
 050221429103811273600060001000609 call to the CROCI API

```
[
  {
    "oci": "050221429103811273600060001000607-
          050221429103811273600060001000609",
    "citing": "br/0601067",
    "cited": "br/0601069",
    "creation": "2008-05",
    "timespan": "P23Y",
    "journal_sc": "no",
    "author_sc": "no"
  }
]
```


Chapter 4

Implementation

This chapter introduces an overview of the implementation of the expansion of CROCI. First, it presents the updated OpenCitations Index Software Library, its structure and functionalities, and the new software developed for satisfying the requirements for CROCI. Then, the OC libraries that were employed, `oc_meta` and `oc_graphenricher`, are described.

4.1 The OpenCitations Index Library

The OpenCitations Index Library¹ has been implemented by OC to create, manage, and update the OC Indexes. Released under an open license (ISC license²) and written in Python³ and, for a smaller part, C++, the library serves multiple purposes for the creation of citation data. All the software in OC is released with an open license, the ISC license, that allows unrestricted use and distribution.

Recently, the library has undergone significant changes to make it more sustainable and to allow multiprocessing. To guarantee consistency within the library as well as polymorphism, the general structure of each structure in OC Index consists of a base abstract base class (e.g. `IdentifierManager`) that acts as a base for later specific instantiations (e.g. `DOIManager`).

¹OpenCitations: Index <https://github.com/opencitations/index> last accessed 15/10/2022

²ISC License <https://opensource.org/licenses/ISC> last accessed

³Python <https://www.python.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

The current version (described in Figure 4.1) contains the following groups of software:

- **scripts**: scripts that are used for launching the processes in the index library.
- **index**: the software content that contains the classes and scripts that are then employed when launching the scripts. Here there are two subdirectories: **cpp**, that contains C++ software that is used as support, and **python**, containing the main software.

The `index/src/python` folder contains:

- **finder**: Scripts that manage the gathering of information of resources from APIs (e.g. Crossref).
- **glob**: Scripts that are used before parsing to create valid input files for the creation of COCI, DOCI and NOCI.
- **identifier**: Scripts that manage identifiers such as DOIs. These manage both validity and normalisation of a given ID.
- **oci**: Scripts that manage the `Citation` class modelled after the `cito:citation` entity.
- **parsing**: Scripts that are used for parsing citation data. These include the software that creates the indexes such as COCI, CROCI and NOCI.
- **preprocessing**: Scripts that are used for preprocess data before the parsing scripts
- **utils**: Other software utilities.
- **validate**: software for validating OCIs and remove duplicates.

The library is also designed to be used from the command line. To allow this, a user needs to install the library following these steps:

- First, install CMake⁴ and libzip⁵.

⁴CMake <https://cmake.org/> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁵Libzip <https://github.com/nih-at/libzip> last accessed 15/10/2022

- In the command line, type the command `make build` to build the binaries for creating
- Use `sudo make install` to add the binaries to the `$PATH`
- Use `pip install .` to install the library’s dependencies and commands

Having done this, it is possible to use the library from the command line. The commands for launching the various processes the OC Index services can be found in Table 4.1.

<code>oc.index.cnc</code>	Create New Citation: this command manages the process for creating citation data from a given input. <code>cnc</code> is the main software for creating citation data, managing the multiple services. It employs multiprocessing to elaborate multiple source files at the same time.
<code>oc.index.datasources</code>	This scripts manages the migration of data from CSV to Redis for managing the creation of citation data.
<code>oc.index.glob.crossref</code>	This command launches the glob script for processing JSON files obtained from Crossref to create support files for COCI.
<code>oc.index.glob.doci</code>	This command launches the glob script for processing JSON files obtained from DataCite to create support files for DOCI.
<code>oc.index.glob.noci</code>	This command launches the glob script for processing JSON files obtained from DataCite to create support files for DOCI.
<code>oc.index.trim_crossref</code>	This command is used to process Crossref JSON files and trim them according to the value contained in the metadata specified in input.
<code>oc.index.validate</code>	This command is used to process Crossref JSON files and filter to remove existing citations.
<code>oc.index.checkmetadata</code>	This command checks the metadata from Crossref to filter the files created after a certain date.
<code>oc.index.oci</code>	This command validates an OCI and retrieves citation data associated with it.

Table 4.1. Table of commands within the OC Index library

4.2 The OpenCitations Meta library

For the process to be carried out, CROCI needs to interface with OC Meta and, to do so, it needs to use the `oc_meta` software library⁶ that manages the creation and processing of documents for OC Meta. To launch it correctly, two elements are needed:

1. A SPARQL endpoint to which the generated triples are uploaded. Since OC Meta is not yet online, a local instance was used. To create such instance, it is also possible to download Blazegraph and run it by using the command line command: `java -jar blazegraph.jar`
2. A YAML configuration file containing the information to launch OC Meta.

The OC Meta process can also be launched from the command line by using by `python -m oc_meta.run.meta_process -c <PATH>` where PATH is the path to the configuration file.

The configuration file contains information about the input directory where the CSV files to be uploaded to OC Meta are contained and where the output files will be contained. The input YAML file used in the current version of CROCI indicates for the input directory the `meta` subdirectory in the `croci_tmp` directory, which is where the temporary files for CROCI are stored. The output folder was set to the output folder in the parent directory where the process is launched; inside, after the process is launched, four directories will be created; of these, the CSV one will contain the CSV file processed by OC Meta and with the MetaID.

4.3 OpenCitations Graphenricher

The `oc_graphenricher`⁷ library was developed as part of the Wikipedia Citations in Data initiative; it is a tool that allows to enrich any OCDM compliant Knowledge Graph with information gathered from multiple sources, like Crossref, Wikidata,

⁶OpenCitations Meta Software https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta last accessed 15/10/2022

⁷`oc_graphenricher`, https://github.com/opencitations/oc_graphenricher last accessed 17/10/2022

VIAF and ORCID. It is also able to perform instance matching and deduplication of bibliographic resources, responsible agents and IDs. Normally, this library is used on graph objects to, as the name suggests, enrich with information from different services.

In the case of the current version of CROCI, its interfaces with ORCID and VIAF APIs were used to get information from these services, as they were convenient for easily gathering IDs for authors given resource identifiers or other bibliographic information.

4.4 The new classes and scripts

This section goes through the scripts and classes that have been created to deal with the steps described in the Methodology section. For the functions that were introduced in this version, a flowchart was created to describe their logic.

4.4.1 IdentifierManager classes: MetaIDManager, ISBN-Manager and WikidataManager

To manage the multiple IDs that could be used in the citations, three new subclasses of the `IdentifierManager` subclasses were added to the OC Index library:

- `MetaIDManager` for the MetaIDs.
- `WikidataIDManager` for QIDs.
- `ISBNManager` for ISBNs. This was gathered from an earlier version of OC Meta.

These classes are employed to normalise existing input IDs. As such, the `normalise` method is used. This is important to harvest data that is consistent with the standards of OC.

4.4.2 ResourceFinders Classes: MetaFinder and WikidataFinder

For the `ResourceFinder` classes, two subclasses were added to address the needs in CROCI.

The `MetaFinder` is a subclass of the `ResourceFinder` subclass that allows to gather information easily from OC Meta’s REST API given a `MetaID`. This class is not part of the parsing and preprocessing workflow described here, but it is used to integrate CROCI with the latest integration of the index software library. It allows the user to gather bibliographic information used in the creation of new citation data, as the other `ResourceFinder` subclasses do.

The `WikidataFinder`, also a subclass of `ResourceFinder` is used to gather information from Wikidata. It needs to gather information through a SPARQL query rather than querying a REST API through an identifier and should manage multiple types of it, while guaranteeing the same behaviour as other `ResourceFinder` subclasses. This class is crucial in CROCI to gather other IDs, since Wikidata, compared to Crossref and DataCite, is able to store any ID thanks to it being a triplestore. Potentially, it could also be used for other citation indexes, e.g. to ingest citations from Wikidata.

4.4.3 IDPopulator

The `IDPopulator` class present in the preprocessing directory is responsible for the processing of an ID, first by validating and normalising it, then by gathering other identifiers. To do so, it queries the Wikidata SPARQL endpoint with one of the given IDs. Moreover, it needs to keep track of the ids that were already seen to avoid redundance. This check is done both at the start and at the end of the process since there are cases where the association between identifiers is not bidirectional.

4.4.4 MetadataPopulator

The `MetadataPopulator` class chooses the services to query depending on the IDs given by using the `ResourceFinders`. The results of the APIs, obtained in JSON format, were preprocessed and mapped by other preprocessing scripts:

- `wd_preprocessing`: function that preprocesses the results from Wikidata’s queries. It needs to gather map the type of the resource of Wikidata to the name of resources as they are used in OC. The mapping is listed in Table...
- `datacite_preprocessing`: function that preprocesses the results obtained by querying DataCite’s REST API through the `DataCiteResourceFinder`.

Figure 4.2. Representation of the logic behind the IDPopulator

The mapping for types is shown in Table ...

- For Crossref, the OC Meta plugin `CrossrefProcessing` was used for to create the file in the correct format.

If DOIs are present, Crossref and DataCite are used for gathering information. If no result is found or no DOI exists for the resource, then Wikidata is queried. If no QID is present, an empty dictionary is created with all the fieldnames. This is done because it might be the case that no information was found, but there is information on OC Meta.

Wikidata Entity	Type
Q13442814	journal article
Q18918145	journal article
Q1266946	dissertation
Q7318358	journal article
Q215028	journal article
Q193495	monograph
Q13136	reference book
Q23927052	proceedings article
Q1980247	book chapter
Q1172284	dataset
Q1711593	edited book
Q277759	book series
Q121769	reference entry
Q28062188	book set
Q317623	standard
Q265158	peer review
Q3331189	book
Q7725634	book

Table 4.2. Wikidata entity to OC type mapping.

4.4.5 AuthorPopulator

The AuthorPopulator class retrieves identifiers connected to authors of resources; in particular, it retrieves their ORCID and VIAF by using the respective APIs through the `oc_graphenricher` library. The information about the author is stored in a string, with the IDs in square brackets.

Audiovisual	other
Book	book
BookChapter	book chapter
ComputationalNotebook	other
ConferencePaper	proceedings article
ConferenceProceeding	proceedings
DataPaper	other
Dataset	dataset
Dissertation	dissertation
Event	other
Image	posted content
InteractiveResource	posted content
Journal	journal
JournalArticle	journal article
Model	other
OutputManagementPlan	other
PeerReview	peer review
PhysicalObject	other
Preprint	journal article
Report	report
Service	other
Sound	other
Standard	standard
Text	other
Workflow	other
Other	other

Table 4.3. DataCite type mapping to OC types.

4.4.6 MetaFeeder

The `MetaFeeder` class manages the process that translates a citation table in AnyID-to-AnyID format into a MetaID-to-MetaID format employing an interface with OC Meta. Starting from a citation table, it employs with the `IDPopulator` to gather all the IDs connected to the starting ones. Then, it gathers the metadata through the `MetadataPopulator`. Finally, it ‘feeds’ the information to OC Meta and gathers the resulting MetaIDs to create the new citation table. `MetaFeeder` also manages the creation of the temporary files and table for CROCI; in particular, a `croci_tmp` directory, where the resulting AnyID-to-AnyID are stored, is created

Figure 4.3. Representation of the logic behind the `MetadataPopulator`

in the parent folder from where the files is launched, with a subdirectory `meta` that contains the files to be launched to OC Meta.

4.4.7 CrociParser

Finally, the existing parser for CROCI starts the process; given an AnyID-to-AnyID citation, once it parses a file it converts it into a MetaID-to-MetaID citation file, then it parses the row creating a citation item for each of them. The created citation

data is modelled in a CSV table that is inserted in the `index` workflow, with the final citation data in RDF.

4.4.8 Updating the CROCI REST API

A HF file with the specification was developed for updating the REST API for CROCI. The existing API was developed by having in mind DOIs rather than MetaIDs; the new API needs to be compatible with MetaIDs and be able to gather information by communicating with OC Meta. To do so, some of the SPARQL queries need to be completed by using OC Meta's API, in particular for gathering all the metadata that is not stored in CROCI. The advantage here is the fact that, by using an internal service rather than an external one, OC will have more control on the process and the data quality.

4.4.9 Test Driven Development

For developing this software, a Test Driven Development (TDD) strategy was followed. This process ensures that the creation of new software satisfies the requirements defined before coding, and guarantees that any alteration to existing software that might cause other functionalities to break is detected. This is done through an automated process by employing software libraries such as `unittest`⁸ for Python and can be integrated with DevOps tools such as Github Actions.

1. The TDD process starts by creating a test for a new functionality. In the case of CROCI, there was already a test that involved only DOI-to-DOI citations. This test was expanded both in the input and expected result, and new tests were implemented for the preprocess functions.
2. The test is checked with the existing algorithm. If the existing software can correctly manage the new functionality, no modifications are needed.
3. If the test fails, the software needs to be changed by writing the code to correct the test.

⁸unittest library <https://docs.python.org/3/library/unittest.html> last accessed 15/10/2022

4. Once the test succeeds, the other tests need to be checked. If some of these fail, go back to them and modify what is needed.
5. Finally, if all the tests succeed, refactor the code.

For this software, the tests that were developed are:

1. `test_croci_pp`: testing for the preprocessing functions of the IDPopulator, the AuthorPopulator and the MetadataPopulator.
2. `test_croci`: testing for processing a citation table.

These tests consider multiple cases using citations between articles with different ID sources to test the performance on the different services.

Figure 4.4. Representation of the decision tree of the AuthorPopulator

Figure 4.5. Representation of the decision tree for the MetaFeeder

Chapter 5

Technical Implementation

This section delves into technical details about the implementation of the current version of CROCI. For each script that has been developed or modified, a description of the new code introduced are given. The abstract classes can be found in the `base.py` script inside each directory.

5.1 IdentifierManager

The `IdentifierManager` scripts can be found in the “identifier” subdirectory¹. The abstract class, in this case, is `IdentifierManager`. These classes have the purpose of:

- Normalise a given ID in a standard form.
- Verify whether an ID exists through an external API service.
- Keep memory of verified IDs to avoid repeating a check for resources that were already gathered.

Other than the ones listed here, there are two other classes used in CROCI that were not modified:

- `DOIManager`: used for managing DOIs.
- `PMIDManager` used for managing PMIDs

¹identifier <https://github.com/opencitations/index/tree/master/index/python/src/identifier>
last accessed 17/10/2022

5.1.1 MetaIDManager

The `MetaIDManager` class² (see Script 5.1) is a subclass of the `IdentifierManager` class that aims to extend the base functionalities to MetaIDs. In this case, the functionality for the API service were not tested as OC Meta is not yet here. The `normalise` method works for any type of MetaID by keeping the two digits before the forward slash character (“/”). It checks for the existence of a MetaID by sending a request to the URL `https://w3id.org/oc/meta/` with the given MetaID. For now, this service is not working because OC Meta is not yet deployed.

Script 5.1. `MetaIDManager` script

```

from oc.index.identifier.base import IdentifierManager

class MetaIDManager(IdentifierManager):
    def __init__(self, data = {}, use_api_service=False):

        self.p = "meta:"
        self.use_api_service=use_api_service
        self._api = "https://w3id.org/oc/meta/"
        self._data = data
        super(MetaIDManager, self).__init__()

    def is_valid(self, id_string):
        metaid = self.normalise(id_string, include_prefix=True)
        if metaid is None:
            return False
        else:
            if not metaid in self._data
            or self._data[metaid] is None:
                return self.__metaid_exists(metaid)
            return self._data[metaid].get("valid")

```

²MetaIDManager <https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/identifier/metaid.py>
last accessed 15/10/2022

```
def normalise(self, id_string, include_prefix=False):
    try:
        metaid_string = sub("\0+", "", sub("\s+", "",
        unquote(id_string[id_string.index("/")-2:]))
        return "%s%s" % (self.p if
        include_prefix else "",
        metaid_string.lower().strip())
    except:
        # Any error in processing the MetaID will return None
        return None

def __metaid_exists(self, metaid_full):
    if self._use_api_service:
        metaid = self.normalise(metaid_full)
        tentative = 3
        while tentative:
            tentative -= 1
            try:
                r = get(self._api + quote(metaid),
                        headers=self._headers, timeout=30)
                if r.status_code == 200:
                    r.encoding = "utf-8"
                    json_res = loads(r.text)
                    return json_res.get("responseCode") == 1
            except ReadTimeout:
                # Do nothing, just try again
                pass
            except ConnectionError:
                # Sleep 5 seconds, then try again
                sleep(5)

    return False
```

5.2 ISBNManager

The `ISBNManager` class³ extends the normalisation verifications for ISBNs and checks the presence of the correct number of digits. In general, it needs to deal with the possibility of having either type of ISBN (ISBN-10 or ISBN-13) and should allow for having the presence of hyphens since Wikidata stores ISBNs with hyphens. In the end, OC Meta removes them. It is also possible to remove the hyphens by specifying the Boolean parameter `include_hyphens` if needed. As anticipated, this class was introduced here for CROCI but was adapted from `oc_meta`.

5.2.1 WikidataIDManager

The `WikidataIDManager` class⁴ (Script 5.2) manages QIDs given by Wikidata. The `normalise` method checks for the presence of the uppercase Q that is present before any QID. This script can also verify the presence of an ID on Wikidata by sending a request to the URL for a Wikidata entity `http://wikidata.org/entity/` and the QID. This class is useful for any citation index or script that will need to use QIDs

Script 5.2. WikidataIDManager

```

from oc.index.identifier.base import IdentifierManager

class WikiDataIDManager(IdentifierManager):
    '''This class is used to validate WikiData Identifiers.'''
    def __init__(self, data = {}, use_api_service=True):
        super().__init__()
        self._api = "http://wikidata.org/entity/"
        self._data = data
        self.use_api_service = use_api_service
        self.p = "wikidata:"

    def is_valid(self, id_string):

```

³<https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/identifier/isbn.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁴<https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/identifier/isbn.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

```
qid = self.normalise(id_string)

if qid is None:
    return False
else:
    if not qid in self._data or self._data[qid] is None:
        return self.__qid_exists(qid)
    return self._data[qid].get("valid")

def normalise(self, id_string, include_prefix=False):
    try:
        id_string = id_string.upper()
        qid_string = sub("\0+", "", sub("\s+", "",
            unquote(id_string[id_string.index("Q"):])))
        return "%s%s" % (self.p if include_prefix else "",
            qid_string.strip())
    except Exception as e:
        # Any error in processing the WikiData ID will return None
        print(e)
        return None

def __qid_exists(self, qid_full):
    if self.use_api_service:
        qid = self.normalise(qid_full)
        tentative = 3
        while tentative:
            tentative -= 1
            try:
                r = get(self._api + quote(qid),
                    headers=self._headers, timeout=30)
                if r.status_code == 200:
                    r.encoding = "utf-8"
                    json_res = loads(r.text)
                    return json_res.get("responseCode") == 1
```

```
except ReadTimeout:
    pass # Do nothing, just try again
except ConnectionError:
    sleep(5) # Sleep 5 seconds, then try again

return False
```

5.3 ResourceFinder

The `ResourceFinder` base class⁵ and relative subclasses are found in the `finder`⁶ subdirectory. The role of these classes is to query external services given an ID to gather information. There are multiple base classes.

The parent class is the `ResourceFinder`, that provides the structure for other finder classes; it contains a basic constructor, as well as the abstract methods:

- `get_orcid`, that retrieves the ORCIDs relative to the given ID.
- `get_pub_date`, for retrieving the publication date associated to the given ID.
- `get_container_issn`, for retrieving the ISSN of the container.
- `is_valid`, which checks whether the ID is valid.
- `normalise`, which normalises a specific ID.

Other than this, other base classes for `ResourceFinder` include `APIDoiResourceFinder` for APIs that use DOIs and `ResourceFinderHandler` for managing multiple `ResourceFinder` instances that need merging.

⁵<https://github.com/opencitations/index/blob/master/index/python/src/finder/base.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

⁶`finder` <https://github.com/opencitations/index/blob/master/index/python/src/finder/> last accessed 17/10/2022

5.3.1 MetaFinder

The `MetaFinder`⁷ class extends the `ResourceFinder` class to gather information from OC Meta’s REST API. This script was created for integration with the rest of the OC Index library, especially for the `cnc`. It is not implemented within the preprocessing workflow because it is possible that the information that is already present on OC Meta might be wrong.

Script 5.3. MetaFinder

```
class MetaFinder(ResourceFinder):
    """This class is used to query OC Meta's API."""

    def __init__(self, data={},
                 use_api_service=True, id_type="metaid"):
        """
        Args:
            data (dict): support data to use prior to api.
            use_api_service (bool): true whenever you want make
                                   use of api, false otherwise.
        """
        super().__init__(data, use_api_service)

        self._data = data

        config = get_config()
        module, classname = config.get("identifier", id_type)
                               .split(":")
        self.__id_type_manager_class = getattr(
            importlib.import_module(module), classname
        )
```

⁷<https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/finder/meta.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

```
self._dm = self.__id_type_manager_class(data ,
    use_api_service)
self._im = ISSNManager()
self._om = ORCIDManager()

self._headers = {

    "User-Agent": "ResourceFinder_/OpenCitations_Indexes_\

    "(http://opencitations.net;mailto:contact@opencitations.net)"
}
self._use_api_service = use_api_service
self._api = "https://127.0.0.1:5000/api/v1/metadata/"

def get_orcid(self , id_string):

    if not id_string in self._data
        or self._data[id_string] is None:
        return self._get_item(id_string , "orcid")
    else:
        return self._data[id_string]["orcid"]

def get_pub_date(self , id_string):

    if not id_string in self._data
        or self._data[id_string] is None:
        return self._get_item(id_string , "date")
    else:
        return self._data[id_string]["date"]

def get_container_issn(self , id_string):

    if not id_string in self._data
        or self._data[id_string] is None:
```

```
        return self._get_item(id_string, "issn")
    else:
        return self._data[id_string]["issn"]

def is_valid(self, id_string):

    if not id_string in self._data
        or self._data[id_string] is None:
        return self._dm.is_valid(id_string)
    else:
        return self._data[id_string]["valid"]

def normalise(self, id_string):

    return self._dm.normalise(id_string, include_prefix=True)

def _get_item(self, meta_entity, column):
    if self.is_valid(meta_entity):
        metaid = self.normalise(meta_entity)

        if not metaid in self._data:
            json_obj = self._call_api(metaid)

            if json_obj is not None:
                if column == "issn":
                    return self._get_issn(json_obj)
                elif column == "date":
                    return self._get_date(json_obj)
                elif column == "orcid":
                    return self._get_orcid(json_obj)
            return None

    return self._data[metaid][column]
```

5.3.2 WikidataFinder

The `WikidataFinder` class⁸ (Script 5.4) extends the functionalities of the existing `ResourceFinder` to gather information from Wikidata's SPARQL Endpoint . The constructor works somewhat differently from the other `ResourceFinder` classes, as it allows for new queries to be added to the base ones when creating the class.

Script 5.4. WikidataFinder

```

BASE_QUERIES = {
    "base_info" : """
SELECT (GROUP_CONCAT( ?ids; separator = ', ' ) as ?orcid)
       ?issn ?pub_date
WHERE {{OPTIONAL {{ wd:{value} wdt:P123 ?publisher.
                  ?publisher wdt:P236 ?issn }}
      OPTIONAL{{ {value} wdt:P577 ?date.
                  BIND(SUBSTR(str(?date), 0, 5) as ?pub_date)}}
      OPTIONAL {{ {value} wdt:P50 ?author.
                  ?author wdt:P496 ?ids }}
}} GROUP BY ?issn ?pub_date """
}

class WikidataResourceFinder(ResourceFinder):
    '''This class allows for querying Wikidata'''

    def __init__(self, data={}, use_api_service=True,
                 api_key=None, queries = dict()):
        super().__init__(data, use_api_service)
        self.api = "https://query.wikidata.org/sparql"
        self._headers = 'ResourceFinder_/_OpenCitations_Indexes_-'
        self._headers += '(http://opencitations.net;_mailto:contact@opencitations.net)'
        self.sparql = SPARQLWrapper(self.api , agent= self._headers)
        self.valid_queries = dict()

```

⁸<https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/finder/wd.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

```
for el in queries:
    self.valid_queries[el] = queries[el]
self._dm = self.__id_type_manager_class(data,
                                         use_api_service)
```

The `BASE_QUERIES` dictionary contains the base SPARQL query that is used to gather information about a publication, the ORCID of an author, the publication date and the ISSN of the container, if present. The `_call_api` method (Script 5.5) is used to query the endpoint with a query, taking the element to search and the value to be added in the query as keyword arguments, substituted in the query string. Finally, if there are multiple values for a same element depending on the language, the English names are favoured.

Script 5.5. WikidataFinder

```
def _call_api(self, to_search, **kwargs):
    query = self.valid_queries.get(to_search)
    if query is None:
        return None
    try:
        query = query.format(**kwargs)
    except:
        raise ValueError("Not enough values to complete the query")
    self.sparql.setQuery(query)
    self.sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    response = self.sparql.query().convert()
    result = {}
    for el in response['results']['bindings']:
        for variable in el:
            if variable not in result:
                result[variable] = el[variable]['value']
            elif el[variable].get("xml:lang") == "en":
                result[variable] = el[variable]['value']
    return result
```

The items searched here through SPARQL queries used in the preprocessing can be found in the Table 5.1. They consist in queries for gathering each ID depending

on which ID is chosen, for gathering the metadata for a publication given a QID, or to gather a QID itself.

"doi"	Selects a DOI given a QID,
"pmid"	Selects a PMID given a QID,
"isbn"	Selects a ISBN given a QID,
"qid"	Selects a QID given any other identifier.
"metadata"	Gathers bibliographic information available on Wikidata

Table 5.1. SPARQL queries used in the preprocessing.

5.4 Preprocessing

As anticipated, for the preprocessing part there are four different scripts with the `MetaFeeder` acting as the master. They are all found in the `populator.py`⁹ file.

5.4.1 IDPopulator

The `IDPopulator` (Script 5.6) employs `IdentifierManager` and `WikidataResourceFinder` instances to validate and enrich the identifiers that are given in the input query. In the constructor, the `IdentifierManager` instances are instantiated inside a dictionary associated to the prefix used here. Then, a `WikidataResourceFinder` instance is created with the queries for IDs described previously in table Finally, a dictionary and a counter for the number of IDs are instantiated, to keep track of the order in which IDs are validated and found.

Script 5.6. IDPopulator

```
class IDPopulator:
    """This class is responsible for validating and populating a string

    def __init__(self) -> None:
        self.wd_finder = WikidataResourceFinder(queries=ID_WD_QUERIES)
```

⁹<https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/finder/wd.py> last accessed 15/10/2022

```
self.ids = {
    "doi": DOIManager(),
    "pmid": PMIDManager(),
    "wikidata": WikiDataIDManager(),
    "meta": MetaIDManager(),
    "isbn": ISBNManager(),
}
self.seen_ids = {}
self.id_num = 0
```

The `IDPopulator` has three different methods. The one that launches the whole process of validation and aggregation of IDs is `populate_ids` (Script 5.7). This method can return three elements depending on the conditions:

- The ID is valid and was not seen before; it returns a tuple with the ID and an integer of its position.
- The ID is valid and was already in the memory; it returns the position of the ID, so the `validate_ids` method returned an integer. The position is returned.
- The ID is not valid; it returns `None`.

If a new position is assigned, the counter of the position is increased. Storing the IDs is especially important since this index is crowdsourced; we can expect that citing entities will probably be repeated for a number of citations (think of a scholar who sends the bibliography from their paper), meaning that working in this way it will save significant time. This situation also emerged for citations that were already submitted for the previous version of CROCI.

Script 5.7. `populate_ids` method

```
def populate_ids(self, ids: str) -> tuple:
    validated = self.validate_ids(ids)
    if isinstance(validated, int):
        return validated
    elif validated is not None:
```

```

ids = self.complete_ids(validated)
tmp = []
seen = False
pos = self.id_num
for identifier in ids:
    id_n = ids[identifier]
    for id in id_n.split("_"):
        id = f"{identifier}:{id}"
        if id in self.seen_ids:
            seen = True
            pos = self.seen_ids[id]
            continue
        tmp.append(id)
if seen:
    for el in tmp:
        self.seen_ids[el] = pos
    return pos
self.id_num += 1
for el in tmp:
    self.seen_ids[el] = pos
return ids, pos

```

The `validate_ids` (Script 5.8) method gets a string containing ids separated by a semicolon. The IDs are split and each of them is validated by using the normalise methods. Rather than a series of if statements, the normalisation is applied by using a dictionary. If no id is valid, the row is invalidated. The ids are stored in a dictionary and returned. This method is also responsible for checking whether in normalising the IDs an ID that was already stored in the `seen_ids` dictionary is found. If this is the case, the position of the ID in the sequence is returned.

This method is also responsible for checking whether in normalising the IDs an ID that was already stored in the `seen_ids` dictionary is found. If this is the case, the position of the ID in the sequence is returned.

Script 5.8. `validate_ids` method

```

def validate_ids(self, ids:str) -> dict:
    identifiers = {}
    try:
        for id in ids.split(
            ";␣"
        ):
            # first, we check the presence of ids.
            if "'" in id:
                id = id.replace("'", "")
            if '"' in id:
                id = id.replace('"', "")
            prefix_idx = id.index(":")

            prefix, id = id[:prefix_idx], id[prefix_idx + 1 :]
            if prefix in self.ids:
                id = getattr(self.ids[prefix], "normalise")(id)
                if id != None:
                    if f"{prefix}:{id}" in self.seen_ids:
                        return self.seen_ids[f"{prefix}:{id}"]
                    else:
                        continue
                identifiers[prefix] = id
    except:
        return None
    if len(identifiers) == 0: # if no id is present, we return None
        return None
    else:
        return identifiers

```

Finally, the `complete_ids` method (Script 5.9) manages the search for new IDs. First, the possible IDs that were not found are listed. Then, Wikidata’s SPARQL endpoint is used to gather a QID if not present; this is then used to gather other IDs that are associated with the resource. For each ID found in the end, there is another check for presence in the `seen_ids` dictionary, since it might happen that

an ID might appear connected only to one resource.

It is also possible that while gathering the IDs an ID that was already seen is found; this might happen because of problems in gathering the IDs in Wikidata. As an example, this happened for resources that have multiple IDs associated with a resource (e.g. multiple ISBNs for the same book). This check might also be performed by OC Meta, since here only the IDs that were found are used for deduplication

Script 5.9. complete_ids method

```
def complete_ids(self, identifiers: dict):
    missing_ids = list(
        el for el in self.ids if el not in identifiers
    )
    if len(missing_ids) > 0:
        if "wikidata" in missing_ids:
            for key in identifiers:

                possible_wd = self.wd_finder._call_api(
                    "qid", value = identifiers[key]
                )
                if possible_wd is None or len(possible_wd) == 0:
                    if any(char.islower() for char in identifiers[key]):
                        tmp = identifiers[key]
                        identifiers[key] = identifiers[key].upper()
                        completed = self.complete_ids(identifiers)
                        completed[key] = tmp
                    return completed
                else:
                    continue
            if len(possible_wd) > 1:
                raise Warning(
                    f"There is more than one wikidata "\
                    f"id for {identifiers[key]}"
                )
    )
```

```

possible_wd = self.ids['wikidata']
                .normalise(possible_wd["qid"])

if possible_wd is not None:
    identifiers["wikidata"] = possible_wd
    missing_ids.remove("wikidata")
    break

if "wikidata" in identifiers:
    for id in missing_ids:
        new_id = self.wd_finder._call_api(
            id, value = identifiers["wikidata"]
        )

        if new_id is not None and new_id.get(id) is not None
           and new_id.get(id) != "":
            to_add = []
            for el in new_id[id].split("_"):
                to_add.append(getattr(self.ids[id],
                                      "normalise")(el))
            identifiers[id] = "_".join(to_add)
return identifiers

```

5.4.2 MetadataPopulator

The `MetadataPopulator` class (Script 5.10) manages the creation of the table with the information that will later be fed to OC Meta. The class uses multiple `ResourceFinder` instances to gather the information. This is done by querying Crossref and Datacite if a DOI is present and then Wikidata if a QID is present. Within the constructor, an instance of the `CrossrefProcessing` class from `oc_meta` is instantiated for managing the preprocessing of the results from Crossref.

Script 5.10. `MetadataPopulator` class method

```

class MetadataPopulator:
    def __init__(self) -> None:

```

```

self.crossref_processor = CrossrefProcessing()
self.cr_finder = CrossrefResourceFinder()
self.wd_finder = WikidataResourceFinder(queries=VALID_QUERIES)
self.datacite_finder = DataCiteResourceFinder()

```

The main method within the `MetadataPopulator` class is the `launch_service` method (Script 5.11) that manages the process of choosing which service ought to be queried. If a result is found, it is preprocessed by using a dedicated function to create alignment between the multiple sources of information. The logic that this script follows is to give priority to look for information from DOI services, which are already easily integrated within the OC workflow, then to gather information from Wikidata, that might have consistency concerns.

Script 5.11. `launch_service` method class method

```

def launch_service(self, ids) -> dict:
    result = None

    if "doi" in ids:
        # this is a doi
        cr_result = self.cr_finder._call_api(ids["doi"])
        if cr_result is not None:
            result = self.crossref_processor.csv_creator(cr_result)
        elif cr_result is None:
            result = datacite_preprocessing(
                self.datacite_finder._call_api(ids["doi"]), ids)

    if "wikidata" in ids and result is None:
        result = wd_preprocessing(
            self.wd_finder._call_api(
                "metadata", value = ids["wikidata"]), ids
        )

    if result is None:
        result = {}

```

```
for field in FIELDNAMES:
    if field not in result:
        result[field] = ""

id_string = []
for identifier in ids:
    for id in ids[identifier].split("_"):
        id_string.append(f"{identifier}:{id}")
result["id"] = "_".join(id_string)

return result
```

The results from the APIs from Datacite and Crossref and from Wikidata's SPARQL Endpoint are processed with dedicated functions (Scripts 5.12. For Crossref, a function from `oc_meta` is used).

Script 5.12. Preprocessing functions

```
def wd_preprocessing(values, id):
    '''This function preprocess the information retrieved from wikidata'''
    if values is None:
        return None
    values["id"] = id
    if "type_id" in values:
        if values["type_id"].split("entity/")[1]
            in TYPE_DENOMINATIONS_WD:
            values["type"] = TYPE_DENOMINATIONS_WD[
                values.pop("type_id").split("entity/")[1]
            ]
        else:
            values["type"] = ""
            print(
                f"Resource_{type}_{not}_{recognised}_{from}_{Wikidata}:" \
                "{values.pop('type_id')}"
            )
    else:
```

```

        values["type"] = ""
    return values

def datacite_preprocessing(values, id):
    if values is None:
        return None
    result = {}
    result["id"] = id
    authors = []
    for person in values["creators"]:
        if "givenName" in person and "familyName" in person:
            name = ", ".join((person["familyName"],
                              person["givenName"]))
            orcid = ""
            for identifier in person["nameIdentifiers"]:
                if identifier.get("nameIdentifierScheme") == "ORCID":
                    orcid = identifier.get(
                        "nameIdentifier").split("orcid.org/")[1]
                    orcid = f"_{orcid}"
                    break
            name = f"{person['familyName']} \
                ,_{person['givenName']}{orcid}"
            authors.append(name)
    if values["types"].get("resourceTypeGeneral")
        in TYPE_DENOMINATIONS_DATACITE:
        result["type"] = TYPE_DENOMINATIONS_DATACITE[values["types"]
            .get("resourceTypeGeneral")]
    else:
        result["type"] = ""
        val = values["types"].get("resourceTypeGeneral")
        if val is not None:
            print(f"Type_{val}_from_Datacite_not_recognised:_{val}")

```

```
result["publisher"] = values["publisher"]

result["author"] = ";".join(authors)

result["title"] = values["titles"][0]["title"]

result["pub_date"] = str(values["publicationYear"])

return result
```

5.4.3 AuthorPopulator

The `AuthorPopulator` class (Script 5.13) instantiates in the constructor the APIs for ORCID and VIAF from `oc_graphenricher` and uses the information gathered by the `MetadataPopulator` to complete the information about authors:

- To gather the ORCID, it exploits the presence of an ID associated with the author. The ORCID can be gathered by giving in input to the query method of the ORCID query interface of `oc_graphenricher` a tuple containing a list in the format: `[(lastname, firstname, None, None)]` and an identifier in the format `[(GraphEntity.iri_id, id)]` (for now just DOIs and PMIDs are used) and returns a list in the format `[(lastname,firstname, orcid,None)]`. If no ORCID is found, the tuple is returned identical.
- To gather a VIAF, it uses the title of the resource associated with the author. The VIAF is gathered by giving in input to query method of the VIAF query interface of `oc_graphenricher` the last name, the first name and the name of the resource associated with the author. It returns the VIAF string if found, otherwise `None`.

Script 5.13. `AuthorPopulator` class

```
class AuthorPopulator:
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        self.viaf_api = VIAF()
        self.orcid_api = ORCID()
```

```

def get_author_info(self, ids:dict, resource:dict) -> str:
    authors_complete = []
    for author in resource["author"].split(";"):
        if 'orcid:' in author and 'viaf:' in author:
            authors_complete.append(author)
            continue
    author_ids = {}
    if "[" in author: #if there is an identifier:
        author, identifiers = author.split("[")
        for el in identifiers[:-1].split("):
            prefix, el = el.split(":")
            author_ids[prefix] = el
    try:
        last_name, first_name = author.split(",")

    except ValueError:
        authors_complete.append(author)
        continue
    author_list = [(first_name, last_name, None, None)]
    if "orcid" not in author_ids:
        if "doi" in ids:
            author_list = self.orcid_api.query(
                author_list, [(GraphEntity.iri_doi, ids["doi"])]
            )

        elif "pmid" in ids:
            author_list = self.orcid_api.query(
                author_list, [(GraphEntity.iri_pmid, ids["pmid"])]
            )
        if author_list[0][2] is not None:
            # If an orcid is found, add it
            author_ids['orcid'] = author_list[0][2]
    if "viaf" not in author_ids:

```

```

        possible_viaf = self.viaf_api.query(
            first_name, last_name, resource["title"]
        )
        if possible_viaf != None:
            author_ids['viaf'] = possible_viaf
author_ids = "□".join(f'{k}:{v}'
                    for k,v in author_ids.items())
author = f"{last_name},□{first_name}□[{author_ids}]"
authors_complete.append(author)
return ";□".join(authors_complete)

```

5.4.4 MetaFeeder

The `MetaFeeder` class (Script 5.14) manages the overall task of preprocessing, launching the populating functions listed above as well as managing the interface with OC Meta. The class also creates a `MetaProcess` instance. On creation, it also creates (and clears if already present) the `croci_tmp` directory, where the subdirectory `meta` will contain the files used in the `meta_process`.

Script 5.14. `MetaFeeder` class

```

class MetaFeeder:
    def __init__(self, meta_config=join("..", "meta_config.yaml"))
    -> None:
        self.id_populator = IDPopulator()
        self.metadata_populator = MetadataPopulator()
        self.author_pop = AuthorPopulator()
        self.citations = []
        self.meta_process = MetaProcess(config=meta_config)
        self.meta_folder = join("..", "output")
        self.tmp_dir = join("..", "croci_tmp")
        if not os.path.isdir(self.tmp_dir):
            os.mkdir(self.tmp_dir)
        if not os.path.isdir(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta")):
            os.mkdir(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta"))
        self.clean_dir()

```

The `parse` method manages the input citation files. Each row is parsed by launching the `run` method; this processes the rows in input, and each entity is sequentially stored in the `to_meta` list, while the citation indexes are stored in a tuple in the `citations` list. When all the rows are parsed, `to_meta` is used to create a CSV file with the name of the input file preceded by `"from_"` and with `"_to_meta"` at the end. This is processed by launching the OC Meta process; in the end, the resulting file contains the name of the input file (the words before and after the file were added to avoid possible mistakes in this stage). The file from OC Meta is stored in the `meta_info` list. Finally, the process iterates over the `citations` list and, by using the positions indicated for the citation tuple, the index of the information is gathered. Since OC Meta processes the files and returns them in the same order, the information is solid through the process.

Script 5.15. `parse` method

```
def parse(self, file) -> str:
    '''This method manages the parsing of input files.'''
    to_meta = []
    citations = []
    with open(file, "r") as input:
        reader = csv.DictReader(input)
        for row in reader:
            populated = self.run(row)
            if populated is not None:
                to_meta.extend(populated[0])
                citations.append(populated[1])
    file_to_meta = file
    file_to_meta = file_to_meta.split(sep)[-1]
    file_to_meta = f"from_{file_to_meta[:-4]}_to_meta.csv"
    with open(
        join(self.tmp_dir, "meta", file_to_meta),
        "w+",
        encoding="utf8",
    ) as w:
        writer = csv.DictWriter(w, fieldnames=FIELDNAMES)
        writer.writeheader()
```

```
    for row in to_meta:
        writer.writerow(row)
run_meta_process(self.meta_process)
#os.remove(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta", file_to_meta))
meta_info = []
for dirpath, _, filenames in os.walk(join(self.meta_folder, "csv")):
    for el in filenames:
        if file_to_meta[:4] in el:
            meta_info = (get_data(join(dirpath, el)))
            os.remove(join(dirpath, el))
            break
with open(join(self.tmp_dir, file_to_meta), "w+") as output:
    writer = csv.DictWriter(
        output,
        fieldnames=(
            "citing_id",
            "citing_publication_date",
            "cited_id",
            "cited_publication_date",
        ),
    )
    writer.writeheader()

    for citation in citations:

        to_write = {}
        citing = meta_info[citation[0]]["id"].split('meta:')[1]
        cited = meta_info[citation[1]]["id"].split("meta:")[1]
        to_write["citing_id"] = f"meta:{citing}"
        to_write["citing_publication_date"] = meta_info[citation[0]]["date"]
        to_write["cited_id"] = f"meta:{cited}"
        to_write["cited_publication_date"] = meta_info[citation[1]]["date"]
        writer.writerow(to_write)
```

```

self.id_populator.id_num = 0
return join(self.tmp_dir, file_to_meta)

```

The `run` method (Script 5.16) manages the various steps towards populating the input files for the OC Meta process. It employs the `IDPopulator` first, and if the IDs in a row are not valid, it discards the citation. Then, a dictionary containing the bibliographic information is created with the `MetadataPopulator`. The dates given in input from the citation table are used here if no valid date was given. Finally, information about the authors is gathered by using the `AuthorPopulator`. It returns the row with the new information and the position for the citation.

Script 5.16. `run` method

```

def run(self, row: dict) -> tuple:
    found_ids = []
    result = []
    ids = {
        row.get("citing_id"): row.get("citing_publication_date"),
        row.get("cited_id"): row.get("cited_publication_date"),
    }
    this_citation = []
    for start_id in ids:
        id = self.id_populator.populate_ids(start_id)

        if id == None:
            return None # if one of the ids is invalid, break the process
        elif isinstance(id, int): # change
            this_citation.append(id)
            continue
        else:
            this_citation.append(id[1])
            id = id[0]
            id["start_id"] = start_id
            found_ids.append(id)

    for i in range(len(found_ids)):

```

```
id = found_ids[i] # get each id

date = ids[id.pop("start_id")] # get the date in input for each

# this launches the pipeline
pop_row = self.metadata_populator.launch_service(id)
pop_row["author"] = self.author_pop.get_author_info(id, pop_row)

if pop_row.get("pub_date") is None:
    pop_row["pub_date"] = date
result.append(pop_row)

return result, this_citation
```

The `clean_dir` method functions as a utility to empty the temporary folders to avoid possible errors in parsing.

```
def clean_dir(self) -> None:
    self.id_populator.seen_ids = {}
    if os.path.exists(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta")):
        shutil.rmtree(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta"))
    os.mkdir(join(self.tmp_dir, "meta"))
```

5.5 Parsing

Here, the `crowdsourced.py`¹⁰ script was modified to manage the new MetaID-to-MetaID citations while taking in input the citation tables in AnyID-to-AnyID format.

5.5.1 CROCIParser

The `CrowdsourcedParser` class (Script 5.17) was not changed significantly, except the constructor and parse methods. The current version initialises, instead of a

¹⁰CROCI <https://github.com/dbrembilla/index/blob/master/index/python/src/parsing/crowdsourced.py>
last accessed 19/10/2022

DOIManager, a MetaIDManager and a MetaFeeder instances. The parse method of the latter is used to generate the input file for CROCI, which is then parsed again to create the citation data ready for creating RDF files.

Script 5.17. CrowdsourcedParser class

```
class CrowdsourcedParser(CitationParser):
    def __init__(self, meta_config = join("..", "meta_config.yaml")):
        super().__init__()
        self._rows = []
        self._metaid_manager = MetaIDManager()
        self._meta_feeder = MetaFeeder(meta_config=meta_config)

    def is_valid(self, filename: str):
        super().is_valid(filename)
        return filename.endswith(".csv")

    def parse(self, filename: str):
        super().parse(filename)
        filename = self._meta_feeder.parse(filename)
        with open(filename, "r") as fp:
            self._rows = list(DictReader(fp))
        self._items = len(self._rows)

    def get_next_citation_data(self):
        if len(self._rows) == 0:
            return None

        row = self._rows.pop(0)
        self._current_item += 1
        citing = self._metaid_manager.normalise(row.get("citing_id"),
                                                include_prefix=True)
        cited = self._metaid_manager.normalise(row.get("cited_id"),
                                                include_prefix=True)
```

```
    if citing is not None and cited is not None:
        citing_date = row.get("citing_publication_date")
        if not citing_date:
            citing_date = None

        cited_date = row.get("cited_publication_date")
        if not cited_date:
            cited_date = None
        return citing, cited, citing_date, cited_date, "", ""

    return self.get_next_citation_data()
```

5.6 CROCI API and RAMOSE

CROCI’s API allows for an easy querying of CROCI’s dataset, hiding the complexity of SPARQL queries through the interface built with RAMOSE. The main difference between how the API worked with DOIs and how it works in the current version is the use of multiple IDs and the gathering of metadata by means of services external to the OC infrastructure for gathering information. The new API exploits the existence of OC Meta’s API for the metadata, while adding informations about citations. As anticipated, the main advantage comes in the form of internalising metadata from external services, but also maintaining the consistency of form across OC services. The update was mainly done by modifying the `croci_v1.hf` file in OC’s `api` repository on GitHub¹¹. This also offers the chance of explaining how RAMOSE works, since part of this thesis work was creating its documentation, build the package on PyPi and creating tests.

RAMOSE configuration files are in the HF format. Each row is a key-value pair, with the character “#” before the key (e.g. `#method get`). Each RAMOSE configuration file is composed of two parts: first a description of the API, then the description of each operation.

¹¹OpenCitations APIs <https://github.com/opencitations/api> last accessed 15/10/2022 . For the current version of CROCI’s API, see <https://github.com/dbrembilla/api/tree/croci-v2>

To launch a RAMOSE REST API locally, after downloading the package with `pip(pip install ramose)`, you can use the command:

```
python -m -s path/to/config.hf
```

A description on how to create the configuration file can be found in RAMOSE's documentation¹². In this case, the operations used are the same as for CROCI, but with any ID rather than DOIs. These are the operations available in the updated CROCI API:

- `/references/schema/id`: this operation gathers the data for outgoing references to other cited works found in the reference list of the resource identified by the input ID.
- `/citations/schema/id`: this operation gathers the data for incoming references from other works to the resource identified by the input ID.
- `/oci/oci`: this operation retrieves the citation metadata for the citation identified by the input OCI.
- `/metadata/schema/ids`: this operation retrieves the metadata for a given list of resources specified by the input IDs separated by a double underscore (“__”), gathered thanks to OC Meta's API.
- `/citation-count/schema/id`: this operation retrieves the number of citations received in CROCI by the resource specified by the input ID.
- `/reference-count/schema/id`: this operation retrieves the number of items references by the resource specified in input.

The metadata operation formerly depended on DataCite and Crossref, as it gathered the information dynamically from their APIs. Now, due to the change in the identifiers in CROCI, the service needs to gather the information about input files from OC Meta's API. This process was changed by adding two new functions, the `oc_metadata` and the `__metaid_parser` functions (Script 5.18), that take the MetaID as input and gathers the information about the metadata, while data about citations is collected from CROCI's SPARQL endpoint.

¹²RAMOSE <https://ramose.readthedocs.io> last accessed

Script 5.18. `oc_metadata` and `__metaid_parser` functions

```
def oc_metadata(res):
    # Given an ID, gather its metadata
    header = res[0]
    metaid_field = header.index("br")
    additional_fields = ["author", "year", "title",
                        "source_title", "volume",
                        "issue", "page", "source_id"]

    header.extend(additional_fields)

    rows_to_remove = []

    for row in res[1:]:
        citing_maid = row[metaid_field][1]

        r = None
        if r is None:
            r = __metaid_parser(citing_maid)

        if r is None or all([i in ("", None) for i in r]):
            rows_to_remove.append(row)
        else:
            row.extend(r)

    for row in rows_to_remove:
        res.remove(row)

    return res, True

def __metaid_parser(id):
    api = "127.0.0.1:5000/metadata/%s"
    try:
        r = get(api % id,
```

```
headers={"User-Agent": "CROCI_REST_API" \
        "(via OpenCitations)" \
        "http://opencitations.net;mailto:con" \
        timeout=30)
if r.status_code == 200:
    json_res = loads(r.text)
    return [json_res["id"], json_res["date"],
            json_res["title"], json_res["venue"],
            json_res["volume"], json_res["issue"],
            json_res["page"], id]

except Exception as e:
    pass # do nothing
```

Chapter 6

Evaluation

This chapter presents an evaluation on the overall performance of the software. This chapter is important to understand computational cost for creating CROCI, especially considering that it will be part of the overall OC Index architecture. The first section introduces the hardware used for the test. The second section describes the sample of data that was employed. Lastly, the results found from the querying are presented. The identifiers found and which services were used when querying the sample are also discussed.

6.1 Hardware

The performance of software depends on multiple factor. One of the most impactful ones is the hardware employed; The evaluation process depends on multiple factors, especially considering the fact that CROCI depends on several external services, but also on the hardware used for launching the process.

The operation executed is the creation of citation data by using the `oc.index.cnc -s CROCI` command; it was performed on a Lenovo Ideapad 5 with an Intel Core i7 CPU and 8 GB of RAM and with a 1 GHz internet connection.

6.2 Data Sampling

The sample of data used is based on the CROCI citation data that was crowd-sourced on Github issues from March 2019 to the 1st of September 2022 (aggregated in `croci_doi.csv`) and sample citations gathered from Wikidata through different queries to gather different combination of IDs for balancing the services that are queried; the resulting sample, composed of 5 files of about 80 citations, is available on Zenodo (Brembilla, 2022). The overall sample comprised 405 citations between 470 different entities.

Since CROCI’s preprocessing employs a system for caching the entities and thus avoiding multiple queries for the same IDs, it is important that the citation data is evaluated both for the number of citations and the number of entities. The composition of the resulting datasets is shown in table 6.1.

6.3 Analysis

Table 6.4 shows the time it took to process each file on an average of 10 tests. The time allocated is described both in terms of time per citation and per entity, as the caching system in the preprocessing makes it faster to process the citations. Overall, the time allocated for each entity is under 2 seconds. The results, compared to other indexes, are that the processing of citations is slower (see Moretti, 2022); this comes from the computational cost of querying multiple services to translate the IDs to MetaIDs through OC Meta. However, we can expect batches of information from scholars to be smaller compared to the ones given systematically by services like Crossref, thus making the process more sustainable.

The distribution of IDs that were found from the existing ones are shown in table 6.2. In the sample used, the most found IDs were QIDs (which was to be expected, since most of the samples were gathered from Wikidata) and DOIs, while the ISBNs are the least common. Table 6.3 shows the distribution of services that were queried for gathering bibliographic information. Overall, the sample queried mostly Crossref (especially for entities with DOIs) and Wikidata. In general, the samples containing only DOIs performed faster compared to ones that employed SPARQL queries to Wikidata.

File	Citations	Citing Entities	Cited Entities	Overall Entities
croci_doi.csv	85	8	84	92
croci_isbn.csv	80	47	53	94
croci_isbn_doi.csv	80	23	71	94
croci_pmid.csv	80	13	80	93
croci_pmid_isbn.csv	80	71	49	120

Table 6.1. Dataset description for each file

File	DOI	Wikidata	PMID	ISBN
croci_doi.csv	83	42	6	-
croci_isbn.csv	4	94	-	94
croci_isbn_doi.csv	82	85	17	3
croci_pmid.csv	85	93	93	-
croci_pmid_isbn.csv	71	120	72	47
Overall	69%	92%	48%	30%

Table 6.2. Distribution of IDs retrieved and found in the sample

File	Crossref	DataCite	Wikidata	No bibliographic data
croci_doi.csv	63	17	-	3
croci_isbn.csv	4	-	85	2
croci_isbn_doi.csv	79	3	3	-
croci_pmid.csv	84	-	8	-
croci_pmid_isbn.csv	71	-	47	2
Overall	64%	5%	30%	1%

Table 6.3. Distribution of services used for gathering bibliographic data for the sample

File	Time(s)	Time per citation(s)	Time per entity(s)
croci_doi.csv	154	1.81	1.67
croci_isbn.csv	170	2.13	1.80
croci_isbn_doi.csv	161	2.01	1.71
croci_pmid.csv	164	2.05	1.76
croci_pmid_isbn.csv	235	3	1.96

Table 6.4. Performance of parsing for each file.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and future perspectives

This thesis's objective was to extend the current OC Index software for expanding the citation data handled by CROCI from a DOI-to-DOI citation index to an inclusive AnyID-to-AnyID citation codebase. To enable this extension and making it coherent to the rest of the OC infrastructure, an interface with OC Meta was needed, as well as the creation of a preprocessing pipeline which included a data gathering process from external sources., in the form of identifiers and bibliographic metadata. The result was the update of CROCI and the addition of multiple scripts to the OC index library. Since the work of CROCI strictly depends on OC Meta, once the latter will be running OC will be able to actively integrate the current version of CROCI with the rest of the OC Indexes.

The current software was tested on a small sample that did not take full advantage of the possibilities given by the multiprocessing added in the latest version of the index software library. A bigger dataset might give more accurate benchmarks to the ones provided.

The evolution of CROCI is related to the objectives of OC, depending on its strategy regarding the ingestion of bibliographic data for OC Meta and for the expansion of the indexes towards non-DOI citations. However, CROCI is not yet a universal AnyID-to-AnyID citation index since only DOIs, PMIDs, ISBNs, QIDs and MetaIDs are used in the current version, while new identifiers might be included in the future. Part of the solution to this problem will be the possibility

of registering resources on OC Meta and gather MetaIDs.

7.1 Future Developments

For CROCI to truly handle AnyID-to-AnyID citation data, there needs to be a way to extend the IDs that have been considered until now to new ones, or to gather information from new sources of data. This section contains the possible future development of CROCI in this sense.

7.1.1 Adding new IDs

To add a new ID to the ones available for the input table, first a new `IdentifierManager` class should be created. Then, an instance of this class should be added inside the `self.ids` dictionary in the `IDPopulator` class with the prefix associated to it. A strategy for retrieving the new ID as well as other IDs associated with the said resource should be thought of, e.g. by adding a new ID query for Wikidata if the ID is available there. Finally, if by adding this new ID it will be possible to gather information through new services such as new APIs, extending the `MetadataPopulator` could be useful, as will be described in the following section.

7.1.2 Adding a new source of bibliographic information

Another possible extension might be the extension of the `MetadataPopulator` class to include new sources of bibliographic information, such as a new API. To do so, first, a new `ResourceFinder` class should be created and added to the constructor of the `MetadataPopulator`. Then, the new source should be inserted into the logic of the `launch_service` method of the `MetadataPopulator`. This consideration should come from the evaluation of the different APIs that are used. Finally, the result from the API should be preprocessed for it to be consistent with the metadata standards from OC.

New ID addition pipeline

Figure 7.1. Procedure to add new IDs to the preprocessing for the current version of CROCI

Figure 7.2. Procedure for adding new bibliographic sources to CROCI

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